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Modelling the effect microscale residual stress on acoustoelasticity in carbon fiber composites – Part B: validation and adjustment

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Abstract: This study aims to formulate an ultrasonic longitudinal wave propagation in a unidirectional composite HexTow® AS4/HexPly® 8552, considering the classical laminated theory, residual stresses, mechanical hygrothermal effect, and acoustoelasticity. The approach estimates the velocity for various fiber orientation angles and validates it experimentally. To achieve the proposal, the work was divided into two parts. The theoretical background and the proposed model were the objectives of part A. Part B is dedicated to validating the previously proposed model and proposing adjustment methods. The residual stress generated by the curing process is a possible source of the variation found. The study showed that the and the thermal component during the manufacturing process considerably affects the velocity of the longitudinal wave.

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1. Introduction

The development of Structural Health Monitoring is an area of continuing growth because the use of new materials, as well as new manufacturing processes, demands rigorous tests capable of increasing the reliability of structures made from these new materials [1]. In this context, ultrasound is one of the best cost-effective options compared to other techniques. Besides, it also has great advantages for its versatility because it is a non-destructive technique capable not only of detecting defects, but characterizing the materials and, through the theory of acoustoelasticity, measuring residual stresses and applied stresses.

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According to the Theory of acoustoelasticity, the measurement of the variation in the wave velocity is able to determine the stresses present in the material [2]. For this reason, the development of models that consider effects and behaviors that change the velocity of ultrasonic waves is important to improve the results obtained from acoustoelasticity.

Part A of this study presented a model capable of describing the behavior of longitudinal wave velocities in unidirectional composite materials. Part B of this study proposed to experimentally verify the model found in the previous research, propose a valid adjustment technique and decoupling of the acoustoelastic constants and thermal effects, which were previously understood to be independent effects.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials and methods for the experiments

The samples used in the experimental procedure were manufactured by GME Aerospace, following the best manufacturing practices. The materials used are the HexTow[®] AS4 carbon fiber pre-preg and HexPly[®] 8552 epoxy. Two samples were made, each one with 96 layers with fibers aligned in a unique direction with 18-mm thick. The part was machined to become a 24-sided laminate sample. The procedures involved in manufacturing the samples are detailed in the study by Santos et al. [3][4]. The mechanical properties of the composite are density of 1590 kg/m³; fiber volume of 58.52%; ply thickness of 0.87 mm; longitudinal modulus of 142 GPa; transverse modulus of 9.5 GPa and shear modulus of 5.0 GPa. The geometry of the 24-sided samples was chosen to measure the longitudinal wave velocity in each orientation from the fiber, from -90° to 90°, in 15° increments. The ultrasonic longitudinal wave was generated by a measurement system as presented in Figure 1a.

Fig. 1. Measuring system. (a) equipment and transducers specification (b) clamping system.

The signals obtained in the tests were processed by a program developed on the *Labview*[®] platform, which allows filtering signals. The reference for measuring the time of flight (TOF) of the ultrasonic wave was set at the second intersection with zero [4], i.e., the second time the wave train crosses the zero amplitude point. The tests were conducted by direct transmission at temperatures of 21 °C and 29 °C, in both samples. The position of the transducer on the specimens and its clamping are shown in figure 1b. The processes performed in this study were based on the research group's experience with similar composites. Further details of the measurement procedures can be found in the study by Rodovalho [3].

A 4-term Fourier series was employed to interpolate the wave velocity values for the angles between the measurement points based on the measured results. The goal was to validate the proposed model in part A of this study. The correlation coefficient of this function was $R^2=0.99$. In this way, a model that adequately describes the results of the experiments for any fiber orientation angle was generated.

2.2. Procedure for decoupling thermal effects

In part A of this study a model is reintroduced as shown in Eq. (1):

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho} + \frac{2C_{11}}{\rho} (L_{11}^{t1} \varepsilon_{t1} + L_{11}^{t2} \varepsilon_{t2})}. \tag{1}$$

The way that the thermal deformations in direction 1 (ε_{t1}) and direction 2 (ε_{t2}) are presented may suggest these thermal deformations or stresses are independent, which is not valid. Thermal deformations were generated by the difference between curing temperature and the working temperature of the material. The challenge is precisely decoupling the joint effect of elastic constants L_{11}^{t1} and L_{11}^{t2} , since the temperature variation will cause stress variation in directions 1 and 2. By decoupling these effects, evaluating the contribution of each acoustoelastic constant to the variation in wave velocity is possible. Considering V_0 reference velocity, when the material is free of any stress, the propagation velocity is given by Eq. (2),

$$V_0 = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho}}. \tag{2}$$

From equations (1) and (2), the following procedure was proposed to perform the decoupling of L_{11}^{t1} and L_{11}^{t2} :

- I. Wave velocity without stresses was estimated for all fiber orientation angles using Eq. (2);
- II. Acoustoelastic constant L_{11}^{t1} was estimated for all fiber orientation angles, neglecting the stress in direction 2, using Eq. (3), (4), and (5). Then, the velocities were estimated by Eq.(1), considering only the effect of L_{11}^{t1} , thus eliminating the term $L_{11}^{t2} \varepsilon_{t2}$;
- III. Acoustoelastic constant L_{11}^{t2} was estimated for all fiber orientation angles, neglecting the stress in direction 1, using Eq. (4), (5) and (6). Then, the velocities were estimated by Eq. (1), considering only the effect of L_{11}^{t2} , thus eliminating the term $L_{11}^{t1} \varepsilon_{t1}$;
- IV. The velocity results obtained were plotted, and the decoupling coefficients were proposed based on the least-squares method and graphical analyses.

$$\Delta\sigma_1 = \frac{E_1}{L_{11}^1} \frac{(V - V_0)}{V_0} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \Delta T \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_x \\ \alpha_y \\ \alpha_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = -\Delta T \begin{bmatrix} \alpha E_1 \\ \alpha E_2 \\ \alpha E_3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_2 = \frac{E_2}{L_{11}^2} \frac{(V - V_0)}{V_0} \tag{6}$$

3. Results and Discussions

The velocities in polygonal samples 1 and 2, measured in relation to the orientation of the fibers, and the stress- and strain-free velocity V_0 estimated by Eq. (2) are shown in Figure 2 for measurement temperatures of 21°C.

Fig. 2. Velocity of samples 1 and 2 and velocity estimated by Eq. (4).

In Figure 2, a considerable difference between the measured velocities and stress-free velocity V_0 can be observed; then the material isn't free of stress. This effect was expected and can be explained by the internal stresses arising from the difference between curing temperature (180°C) and working temperature (21 °C). According to the theory of acoustoelasticity, these stresses would cause a difference in wave velocity. Thus, as predicted, the thermal deformations generated by the curing process should not be neglected.

By estimating the stresses and deformations using Eq. (4) and (5) and applying them to Eq. (3), it is possible to estimate the acoustoelastic constants L_{11}^1 . Again using Eq. (4) and (5), now applying them to Eq.(6) to obtain L_{11}^2 , the results should approach the values obtained by measurements in the samples, according to steps I, II and III explained above in item 2.2. The procedure was done for both samples, and the result was similar, so it was chosen to show only the results of sample 1. The results are shown in figure 3a.

Fig. 3. Velocity of samples 1 and the models (a) Comparison Velocity sample 1, Eq. (1) with L_{11}^1 and Eq. (1) with L_{11}^2 (b) Comparison Velocity sample 1, Eq. (7) (c) Comparison Velocity sample 1, Eq. (8) with $fc=0.84$.

Analysing the Figure 3a, it is possible to infer that L_{11}^1 (blue line) generates the best fit in the intervals from -90° to -60° and from 60° to 90°, and L_{11}^2 (red line) the best fit in -45° to 45. Besides, L_{11}^1 or L_{11}^2 show differences in the intervals -60° to -45° and 45° to 60°. The analyses performed so far considered that the thermal stresses acted

in direction 1 or 2. However, they work together, and both contribute to the variation in wave velocity variation. Considering these findings, Eq. 7 was proposed using the previous model with $\sin^2\theta$ and $\cos^2\theta$ functions so that the coefficients have the best fit in the regions mentioned above. The presence of the fc , in the Eq. (7) will be detailed below. The resulting fit is in Figure 3b.

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{C_{111}}{\rho} + \frac{2C_{112}}{\rho} fc(\sin^2\theta \cdot L_{111}^1 \cdot \varepsilon_1 + \cos^2\theta \cdot L_{111}^2 \cdot \varepsilon_2)}. \quad (7)$$

In Figure 3b, factors $\sin^2\theta$ and $\cos^2\theta$ adequately describe the wave velocity variation with $fc=1$. With this adjustment, both the discontinuities occurring at 0° and 90° are no longer present at the estimated velocities.

One must emphasize that the stresses and thermal deformations used in these models were estimated and not measured by experiments, although these equations and coefficients agree with the literature[5]. Thus, slight differences may arise between the estimated and the actual values. In addition, the materials were considered defect-free, with full adhesion between fiber/resin and perfectly straight fibers with precise alignments, requirements that the manufacturing process rarely fully meets. However, as the same behavior is observed in both samples, the effect could not probably be caused by the presence of defects, or the results would be different between samples.

Assuming the existence of sources of differences that cannot be related to the characteristics of the samples used in the experiments, the use of a correction factor fc to be included in the model is justified. The correction factor was obtained using the least-squares method, which shows that 0.84 is the best value. The resulting fit is shown in Figure 3c.

The application of Eq. (7) for the determination of the longitudinal wave velocity has some advantages when considering the characteristics of this type of material. When used in composite materials, the tensile testing equipment required to obtain the acoustoelastic constants requires additional precautions such as precise alignment and attention to edge effects in composites that are not oriented with 0° fibers, among others [6]. The use of Eq. (1) and (7) together with Eq. (3), (4), (5), (6) may mitigate the problems described. Notwithstanding, the acoustoelastic constants obtained using this procedure are only for the internal compressive stresses caused by the thermal effects, being different from the ones used to calculate the stresses applied along the fiber, because this material works differently in tension and compression. How these effects are related to one other is a subject of ongoing studies.

4. Conclusions

The proposed model considers the acoustoelastic formulation and acoustoelastic constants instead of third-order elastic constants, classical laminate theory and the hygro-thermo-mechanical effects. In this work, the model was validated experimentally. The results showed the deformations and thermal stresses generated in the curing process play a role that cannot be neglected in the measurement of velocity and, consequently, in the adjustments of the model to describe the wave behavior.

Also, regarding the proposed model, the inclusion of acoustoelastic constants for internal compressive stress aiming to eliminate the need for the third-order elastic constants from Pao and Gamer's [7] equation may be an effective strategy for composite materials, since the characterization of all those elastic constants involves cutting samples at particular angles and thicknesses, which is not always possible to achieve [8]. However, more work needs to be done to relate these acoustoelastic constants for compressive stresses inside the composite with the one required to calculate the tensile stresses applied along the fibers before eliminating the need for tensile tests for measuring such constant.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Credit author statement

DMG Oliveira: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal Analysis; Writing – draft; Experimental procedure. **VV Gonçalves:** Methodology; Formal Analysis; Experimental procedure. **AA Santos Jr.:** Resources; Supervision; Writing review.

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